

Appendix III
Identified Conflicts

Roles	Conflicting Emotions	Functional Goals
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Advertiser 2. User 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Comfortable; close; empowered 2. Empowered; unpretentious; simple 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Send messages to all pages' followers 2. Delete advertising messages
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Advertiser 2. Government 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Free, careless, sure 2. In control, helpful, powerful 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Track people's data 2. Prevent all kinds of fraud and Be in charge of all the chatbots, or other automatic functions within the messenger
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Advertiser 2. Advertiser 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Wholesome, communal; connected 2. Very individual, independent 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Create individual ads 2. Use the same ads for all users
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Advertiser 2. Government 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Assured; influential; fulfilled, subservient; successful 2. Ruling; successful 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Target non-brand-aware users 2. Restrict advertisers from doing extensive targeting
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Advertiser 2. User 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Heard; connected 2. Calm, isolated 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Host webinars/online events 2. Want app to be as basic as possible
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Advertiser 2. User 3. User 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Powerful, self-governing, smart; successful, assured, free 2. Forceful, involved, respectful, conscious 3. Well-informed'; relatable; free 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Avoid ad blocking 2. Block ads while playing games 3. Filter ads
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Advertiser 2. Government 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Helpful; assistive; caring 2. Supreme; authoritative 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Impact people's choices 2. Impact people's choices
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Advertiser 2. Government 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Frugal; omnipresent; useful 2. Self-indulgent, protected 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Create a "circle" of customers to chat with 2. Move messages from

		3rd parties to spam folder
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. User 2. Government 3. Government 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Assured; safe; strong 2. In control; impetuous 3. Well-informed, empowered; controlling 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Have secret chats 2. Listen to all voice messages 3. Read all the messages from all chats
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. User 2. Government 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Confident 2. Assured; secure; confident 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Edit stories 2. See all messages/stories and etc., which have been edited
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. User 2. User 3. Government 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Engaged, imaginative, competitive, fictional and joyful; connected 2. More realistic, non-competitive; present 3. Assured; in control; powerful, secure, unattached 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Play all kinds of games and Integrate all browser games 2. Remove gaming feature 3. Restrict some games
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. User 2. Government 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Free, safe, unoccupied 2. Assured; safe; strong; close; well-informed 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Restrict some people from seeing any information related to me 2. Get all the detailed information about the person
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. User 2. User 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Forceful; dominant; free 2. Accepted; appreciated 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Delete others' messages 2. Constrain others from deleting my messages